

Impact of galectin-1's redox state on its lectin activity and monomer-dimer equilibrium. Focusing on oxidized Gal-1

Tatiana Staroňová^a, Jitka Holčáková^b, Petr Voňka^b, Roman Hrstka^b, Veronika Ostatná^{a,*}

^a Institute of Biophysics, The Czech Academy of Sciences, v.v.i., Královopolská 135, 61200 Brno, Czech Republic

^b Masaryk Memorial Cancer Institute, Research Centre for Applied Molecular Oncology, Zluty kopec 7, 65653 Brno, Czech Republic

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Galectin-1
Oxidative inactivation
Constant current chronopotentiometric stripping
Intrinsic fluorescence
Lectin activity of reduced and oxidized form
Mobility shift assay

ABSTRACT

Galectin-1 (Gal-1) displays unique sensitivity to oxidative inactivation which appears critical in regulating its spatial and temporal activity. The two physicochemical states, i.e. monomer-dimer equilibrium and redox states, are related to Gal-1 varying functionality. In this work, we used chronopotentiometric stripping analysis, intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy, and mobility shift assay to follow changes in the structure and lectin activity of reduced and oxidized Gal-1 forms. Our results show that monomers and dimers are similarly distributed under mild reduction and oxidation conditions. Gal-1 after its oxidation consists of at least three different monomeric forms while reduced Gal-1 only one. Lectin activity, affinity to *N*-acetylglucosamine, is relatively similar for low Gal-1 concentrations for both, reduced and oxidized Gal-1. However, at higher Gal-1 concentrations, we observed a ten times higher affinity for reduced than oxidized form. Further, our data indicate that the monoclonal antibodies bind preferentially to Gal-1 dimers and specifically to only some forms of its oxidized form.

1. Introduction

Human Gal-1 is a small protein belonging to the evolutionarily conserved glycan-binding lectin family. Carbohydrate binding domains of galectins fold into a three-dimensional structure [1,2] recognizing β -galactoside moieties [3,4]. The binding of lactose to Gal-1 does not alter the protein structure but increases the thermal stability of the Gal-1 and the stability against oxidative damage [1]. At a concentration, where Gal-1 is known to induce most of its biological effect (~ 0.1 – 10 μ M) [5], it coexists in a dynamic monomer-dimer equilibrium [6]. Despite many studies during the first ten years of this century, the relationship between Gal-1 monomer-dimer equilibrium and their biological functions remains inadequately understood [7]. Unlike many other proteins involved in regulating immunity, Gal-1 displays unique sensitivity to oxidative inactivation [8,9], which appears critical in regulating spatial and temporal activity [10]. The two physicochemical states (monomer-dimer equilibrium and oxidized vs. reduced forms) are related to the varying functionality and efficiency of Gal-1 utilized as a therapeutic target [11].

Gal-1 is characterized by the presence of a high number of cysteine residues (six cysteines per monomer, Fig. 1) [13] which are prone to oxidation. This is a reason why most galectins require a reducing

microenvironment to fulfill their function [14,15]. The forming of inter- and intramolecular disulfide bonds between cysteines induces Gal-1 oxidation. Many experiments on Gal-1 oxidation were performed with the mutant proteins, where single or more cysteines were replaced by serines. Cysteine replacements to serines without losing lectin activity pointed out their potential in regulatory processes rather than the involvement in ligand binding. Four cysteines of human Gal-1, namely Cys2, Cys16, Cys88, and Cys130 are solvent-exposed [13]. Ferrer-Sueta et al. [16] suggested that Cys16 residue, among all the solvent-exposed cysteines, might control the onset of the oxidation process as it is the most reactive cysteine at a physiologic pH. Guardia et al. [13] expected that oxidation promoted the formation of the Cys16–Cys88 disulfide bond and multimers through Cys2 [13]. Recent work of Ippel et al. [17] shows that disulfides are formed sequentially, and not randomly, with the first disulfide formation between C16 and C88 [17]. The formation of disulfide bridge C16–C88 results in a conformational change [17–19] allowing to make intramolecular bonds between Cys42 and Cys60, which are buried inside the Gal-1 molecule [7,20]. Fully oxidized Gal-1 forms after the link of the last two cysteines, Cys2 and Cys130 [17].

In this work, we have studied the behavior of native and denatured Gal-1 compared to Gal-1 in its reduced and oxidized state at the charged surface using constant current chronopotentiometric stripping (CPS),

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: ostatna@ibp.cz (V. Ostatná).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijbiomac.2025.139452>

Received 27 September 2024; Received in revised form 20 December 2024; Accepted 31 December 2024

Available online 2 January 2025

0141-8130/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy, and mobility shift assay. The CPS method is a label-free electrochemical method allowing the study of any known proteins on charged interfaces [21,22]. The CPS method is based on the ability of surface-attached proteins to retain their folded structures close to the potential of zero charge but undergo denaturation/unfolding at negatively charged surfaces [23,24]. Protein susceptibility to electric field effects depends on experimental conditions, such as exposure time, ionic strength, and temperature [21]. Protein denaturation/unfolding usually appears during the recording of so-called CPS peak H [25], when the protein is exposed to a potential higher than -1.8 V. Small changes in protein conformation can lead to a variation of the protein stability at a negatively charged interface [22,24], which results in the unfolding of adsorbed protein and thus a relatively high change in CPS peak H compared to the native protein. Proteins consisting of cysteine(s) groups yield so-called peak S, which appears as a result of the reduction of the Hg—S bonds [26]. This peak S can provide information about the presence of Cys and/or Cys—Cys residues [27]. The —SH and —S—S— groups form complexes with mercury and the reductions of —S—Hg and —S—S— Hg complexes take place at different potentials [27]. Thus, peak S position (peak potential) informs about the presence of Cys and/or Cys—Cys residues at the electrode [28,29] and peak S height about their accessibility to electroreduction.

In this work, we first analyzed native and denatured Gal-1 to find the best conditions for structure-sensitive analysis of Gal-1 reduced and oxidized forms. However, using CPS, we found different behavior of Gal-1 treated by reducing and oxidizing agents under various conditions. To explain the obtained results, the CPS data were compared with data from nonreducing polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (PAGE), Western blot, and supplied with lectin activity for *N*-acetyllactosamine determined using intrinsic fluorescence.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

Azodicarboxylic acid bis(dimethylamide) (diamide), tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine hydrochloride (TCEP), hydrogen peroxide, *N*-acetyllactosamine (LacNAc), and urea were purchased from Merck (Czech Republic). All solutions were prepared in triple distilled water. Gal-1 concentration was determined from absorbance taken from UV–Vis spectra at the wavelength of 280 nm, measured by NanoDrop Spectrophotometer ND-1000 (ThermoFisher Scientific, USA).

2.2. Human galectin-1 preparation and purification

The coding sequence of human galectin-1 (NM_002305.4) was cloned using Gateway recombination technology (Invitrogen) into the pDEST15 vector containing an N-terminal His₆-GST tag cleavable by TEV protease (Tobacco Etch Virus nuclear-inclusion-a endopeptidase) and expressed in *E. coli* BL21 RILP. The bacteria were cultured in 100 mL of LB medium (10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract, 5 g/L NaCl) with ampicillin (100 µg/mL) and chloramphenicol (30 µg/mL) overnight at 37 °C, 220 rpm. The culture was diluted to a total volume of 2.5 L in LB medium (supplemented with ampicillin and chloramphenicol) to an optical density at A₆₀₀ = 0.1 and cultured for 2–3 h. Upon reaching an optical density at A₆₀₀ = 0.5, gene expression was induced by the addition of isopropyl-β-D-thiogalactopyranoside to the culture (final concentration 1 mM). The bacterial culture was further cultured for 4 h at 30 °C, 140 rpm, and then pelleted by centrifugation (4000g/4 °C/10 min). Bacterial pellets were resuspended in binding buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5; 0.15 M NaCl, 0.75 % CHAPS). Cell suspensions were subsequently enriched with lysozyme (1 mg/mL), phenylmethylsulfonyl fluoride (1 mM), turbonuclease (1:1000), and MgCl₂ (1 mM), and then sonicated with an ultrasonic sonicator Sonoplus, probe VS 70 T, for 15 cycles (10 s sonication, 50 s pause, 35 W) at 4 °C. Bacterial lysates were obtained by centrifugation for 30 min at 10,000g/4 °C. His₆-GST-tagged proteins were captured on a GSTrap glutathione agarose column (GE Healthcare), eluted with binding buffer enriched with 20 mM glutathione, and subjected to TEV protease cleavage (1 mg of protease per 10 mg of purified protein) overnight at 4 °C. To remove His₆-GST and His₆-TEV protease, protein mixtures were applied to a HisTrap column (GE Healthcare). Fractions containing purified protein were collected in a 96-well plate via a fractionator. After concentration, the protein was solubilized in final testing buffers (25mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 300mM NaCl, and 1 mM TCEP) using Zeba spin desalting columns that separate molecules with a molecular weight up to 10 kDa (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The purity of the isolated protein was verified by SDS-PAGE electrophoresis and staining with Coomassie Brilliant Blue. The TEV protease was prepared in the laboratory following the method from [30].

2.3. Preparation of samples

Gal-1, TCEP, diamide, and hydrogen peroxide were diluted in 30 mM Tris-HCl in the presence of 0.1 M NaCl (pH = 7.4) to their required

Fig. 1. Galectin-1 structure (PDB ID: 1GZW); [12] Gal-1 creates homodimers and each monomer is arranged as a beta-sandwich consisting of two anti-parallel beta-sheets (S-sheets highlighted in yellow color and F-sheets highlighted in red color). Cysteine residues are highlighted in blue color. There is also ligand *N*-acetyllactosamine highlighted in green which is situated close to the binding site of Gal-1. PyMOL software (The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.0 Schrödinger, LLC) was used for visualization of the structure.

concentrations: 2 μM Gal-1, 24 μM TCEP, 5–500 μM diamide, 10 mM hydrogen peroxide. In the ice, Gal-1 was incubated overnight (if not stated otherwise). Denaturation of Gal-1 was achieved by incubating 134 μM Gal-1 in 8 M urea in 30 mM Tris-HCl with 0.1 M NaCl (pH = 7.4) at 4 °C overnight. Denatured Gal-1 was then diluted to a required concentration of 2 μM before the measurement.

2.4. Constant current chronopotentiometric stripping analysis

Electrochemical measurements were performed using an Autolab analyzer (PGSTAT30, EcoChemie the Netherlands) connected to VA-Stand 663 (Metrohm Switzerland) with a three-electrode system. A hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) was used as a working electrode, Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl as a reference, and Pt wire as a counter electrode. The thermostatic cell was set to a controlled temperature of 15 °C, open to air. Obtained data were collected using GPES version 4.9007. Experiments were replicated at least 3 times for each measurement. The incubated samples were adsorbed onto the HMDE electrode surface (0.4 mm²) from a 5 μL drop for an accumulation time t_A of 60 s (if not stated otherwise), at an open circuit potential. Then, the modified HMDE electrode was transferred to a blank electrolyte containing 50 mM Na-phosphate buffer (pH = 7.4). For all measurements, parameters E_B –0.3 V against the Ag|AgCl|3 M KCl for t_B of 5 s and stripping current, I_{str} of –55 μA were selected. All measurements were accompanied by stirring of 1500 rpm during E_B .

2.5. Western blotting and Coomassie brilliant blue staining analysis

For non-reducing PAGE, 2 μg or 5 μg protein (Coomassie blue staining G, CBB) and 50 ng protein (Western blotting) were loaded onto 12.5 % acrylamide gels (12.5 % acrylamide; 372 mM Tris-HCl pH 6.8; 0.027 % APS; 0.07 % TEMED) in 2 \times sample buffer (62.5 mM Tris-HCl pH 6.8; 25 % glycerol; 1 % Bromophenol Blue). PAGE ran for about 1 h at 120 V in the MOPS running buffer (100 mM MOPS, 100 mM Tris base, 7 mM SDS, 2 mM EDTA acid). Gels were stained in Coomassie solution [0.05 % Coomassie Brilliant Blue G 250; 10 % ammonium sulfate; 20 % ethanol (96 %); 12 % orthophosphoric acid (85 %)] overnight and then were destained in H₂O. For Western blotting, the samples were after PAGE transferred to nitrocellulose membranes, blocked with 5 % skimmed milk diluted in PBS supplemented with 1 % Tween for 1 h at room temperature and incubated overnight at 4 °C with primary antibody against galectin-1 (Anti-Galectin 1 antibody [EPR3206(2)]; 1:1000; Abcam, (Galectin-1 Monoclonal antibody (60223-1-Ig), 1:1000; Galectin-1 Polyclonal antibody (11858-1-AP), 1:1000, both Proteintech Group, Inc.). The membranes were washed and probed with horseradish peroxidase-conjugated anti-rabbit secondary antibody (1:1000; Dako) for 1 h at room temperature. Chemiluminescent signals were developed using a mixture of 1:1 ECL-A and ECL-B solutions [ECL-A: 0.5 M EDTA (pH 8), 90 mM coumaric acid, 1 M luminol, 200 mM Tris (pH 9.4) and ECL-B: 0.5 M EDTA (pH 8); 0.123 g NaBO₃ \times 4H₂O; 50 mM CH₃COONa (pH 5)] and visualized with the SYNGENE G:BOX Chem XX6 gel doc system (Syngene; Synoptics Ltd.).

2.6. Fluorescence spectroscopy

The excitation of Gal-1 in PBS buffer (pH = 7.4) with 1000-fold excess of glucose and/or 12-fold excess of TCEP/diamide, was done at 285 nm, and emission spectra were recorded from 302 to 400 nm. All emission spectra were registered using an ISS PC1 photon counting spectrofluorometer (ISS, USA) in a quartz cuvette with a 1 cm path length and at a temperature of 25 °C. The excitation and emission slit widths were fixed at 4 nm each. Fluorescence intensity was normalized; the fluorescence intensity maximum of the Gal-1 complex with LacNAc, I_A , was subtracted from the fluorescence intensity maximum of free galectin titrated with an adequate amount of PBS, I_B . The obtained value was divided by the fluorescence intensity maximum of free Gal-1, i.e.

$(I_B - I_A)/I_B$. The dissociation constant, K_D value, was calculated in Origin Software using the one site-specific binding model $Y = B_{\text{max}} * X/(K_D + X)$, where X is the ligand concentration, Y is the normalized fluorescence intensity, B_{max} is fluorescence intensity at the maximum specific binding and K_D is the equilibrium dissociation constant [31].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Chronopotentiometric stripping analysis of Gal-1

Depending on experimental conditions, the adsorption of a protein on the surface may not lead to dramatic changes in protein structure, therefore we can distinguish between the native and denatured forms of protein [21]. We were interested if we could follow structural changes in Gal-1 treated under various oxidative conditions using chronopotentiometric peak H and peak S. Firstly, we studied native and denatured Gal-1.

Native and urea-treated Gal-1 was adsorbed at the hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) surface for 60 s. Gal-1 modified electrode was transferred to the blank electrolyte, where the chronopotentiogram was recorded. The CPS peak height of native Gal-1 reaches a value of 0.33 ± 0.09 s/V which is, in comparison to the peak height of denatured Gal-1 1.51 ± 0.07 s/V, four times lower (Fig. 2A). Peaks S of native and denatured Gal-1 are similar in heights and potentials (Fig. 2B) suggesting similar oxidation/reduction state of cysteines in both forms [27]. Prolonged adsorption of native Gal-1 leads to an increase of the peak H reaching approximately the same peak area value as its denatured form. Interestingly the peak H height is even higher (Fig. 2C) as an effect of the different structures of chemically denatured Gal-1 and Gal-1 denatured/unfolded by the electric field effects [23,32]. Given experiments are important to correctly set up experimental conditions for analysis of oxidized and reduced Gal-1, under which the structure of Gal-1 will be minimally affected by an electric field. Therefore we chose for the next analysis conditions at which native and denatured Gal-1 can be recognized. At the same time, the native protein is minimally influenced by the effects of an electric field, i.e. at an accumulation time of 60 s.

3.2. Native, reduced, oxidized, and denatured Gal-1

Under the mentioned conditions, we compared the electrochemical responses of Gal-1 reduced by TCEP, widely utilized for storing proteins in their reduced state [33], and of Gal-1 oxidized by diamide and hydrogen peroxide. We choose diamide, which specifically oxidizes cysteine (Cys) residues [34] in contrast to hydrogen peroxide which oxidizes proteins nonspecifically. Although Cys residues belong to one of the most sensitive targets for reactive oxygen species, some other residues are sensitive to oxidation, too [17,35], and can be affected in response to hydrogen peroxide treatment.

Overnight treatment with reducing agent TCEP results in a decrease of peak H height, compared to native Gal-1, by about 25 % (Fig. 3A). The higher peak H of untreated Gal-1 than reduced one could be due to Gal-1 partial oxidation by air during purification. Air oxidation of Gal-1 is a very slow process, which is completely reversible [36]. Peaks H of Gal-1 overnight incubated with 24 μM diamide and 2 h with 10 mM H₂O₂ were similar to the peak of denatured Gal-1 (Fig. 3A). For both oxidized Gal-1, peaks S are smaller and shifted to more negative potentials (Fig. 3B) due to lesser accessibility and a more difficult electroreduction process. On the contrary, higher peaks H of oxidized Gal-1 (Fig. 3A) suggest that electroactive residues of the oxidized Gal-1 are more available for catalytic hydrogen reaction. Accessibility of electroactive residues to electrode processes, in the case of peak S and peak H, could be due to structural changes, different adsorption and orientation of protein [24,37] as well as various distributions of monomers, dimers, and oligomers [35]. To get more information about the distribution of monomers, dimers, and oligomers, we performed a PAGE mobility shift assay under nonreducing conditions (Fig. 3C, D). The TCEP-treated Gal-

Fig. 2. Chronopotentiometric responses of native and denatured Gal-1. A. CPS peak H and B. peak S of 2 μM native (black) and urea-denatured Gal-1 (orange) accumulated at the HMDE surface from 5 μl drop for 60 s, measured in Na-phosphate buffer (dashed line). C. Dependence of peak H area (solid lines, left axis) and height (dashed lines, right axis) on accumulation time.

Fig. 3. Native, reduced, oxidized, and denatured Gal-1. A. CPS peak H heights. The first column shows 2 μM urea-denatured Gal-1 (orange), followed by 2 μM native Gal-1 (black) and Gal-1 which was incubated with 24 μM TCEP (blue)/diamide (red) and 10 mM hydrogen peroxide (green) at $I_{STR} -55 \mu\text{A}$, accumulated at the electrode surface for 60 s. B. Peak S of native Gal-1, urea-denatured Gal-1, and native Gal-1 incubated with TCEP/diamide/hydrogen peroxide. C. CBB G250 staining non-reducing 12.5 % acrylamide gel loaded with 5 μg protein per well, proteins were incubated with 12.5 mM TCEP/diamide/hydrogen peroxide for 2 h at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. D. Western blot analysis of Gal-1 using Anti-Galectin 1 antibody [EPR3206(2)]; 1:1000; Abcam, under the same conditions as in C. Only 50 ng of protein was loaded into each well.

1, in the ratio 1 to 12, yields two distinct bands representing its monomeric and dimeric form, in good agreement with the literature [9,13]. Two protein bands in a similar region are also observed for Gal-1 oxidized with a 12-fold excess of diamide. The oxidized monomeric form is split into three bands, and the dimers' band is slightly enhanced compared to TCEP-treated Gal-1 (Fig. 3C). The massive appearance of higher oligomers is not observed even at a 250-fold excess of diamide (Fig. 4E, F). Western blot assay confirms the findings of the PAGE assay (Fig. 3D). The three bands of oxidized Gal-1 in non-reducing PAGE might represent three different Gal-1 forms with one, two, and three intramolecular disulfide bonds [17]. While individual oxidized Gal-1 forms are not distinctly recognized by Western blot assay (Fig. 3D), the effects of Gal-1 oxidation are still apparent. Fig. 3D shows that the

monoclonal antibodies bind specifically to only some form of oxidized Gal-1. Additionally, antibodies have a preference for dimers. This is evidenced by the stronger antibody signals for dimers relative to monomers in comparison to the total amount of monomers and dimers stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue (Fig. 3C, D). We observed similar results for all tested antibodies (see Section 2.5) not only those from Abcam.

3.3. Oxidation of Gal-1 under various experimental conditions

3.3.1. Diamide concentration

The average height of peak H increases with increasing concentration of diamide applied to Gal-1 for 15 min treatment (Fig. 4). However,

Fig. 4. Gal-1 oxidized and reduced at various ratio of diamide and TCEP. A., C. An average height of the peak H, and B., D. CPS peak H height distributions for different concentration ratios of Gal-1 and A., B. diamide and C., D. TCEP, measured after 15 min of joint incubation. Individual line might represent native – n, denatured – D and unfolded Gal-1 – U. E., G. CBB G250 staining of 2 μ g Gal-1 protein incubated with different concentrations of E. diamide and G. TCEP for 2 h at 4 °C and separated by non-reducing PAGE. F., H. Western blot analysis of Gal-1 under the same conditions as in E and G, 50 ng of protein was loaded into each well after incubation with G. diamide and H. TCEP.

the standard deviation changes from 0.023 s/V for untreated and reduced Gal-1 (Fig. 4A, C) to 0.36 s/V for Gal-1 treated with 500 μ M diamide, which represents the enormous (more than 15 times) increase, suggesting structural changes of Gal-1. We plotted the individual measurements instead of the average peak H values and we found that the peak H distribution of individual measurements varies for different diamide concentrations (Fig. 4B). For the lowest Gal-1, diamide ratio (1:2.5), the particular measurements of peak H are similar to that for untreated Gal-1. With increasing Gal-1, diamide ratio the variation of peak H height increases and peaks H for individual experiments are distributed in several zones. We compared CPS results with mobility shift assays, where band for monomer smeared and new band(s) appeared with increasing diamide:Gal-1 ratio (Fig. 4E). Changes in mobilities of monomers are evident from Western blot, too (Fig. 4F). The amount of dimers is almost constant according to both, non-reducing PAGE and Western blot, suggesting that the changes in peak H height are predominantly influenced by the monomer type.

The peak H heights distributed in several zones resemble the separation of a monomer band in gels. According to the latest knowledge [17], the formation of disulfide C16-C88 has minimal effect on Gal-1 folding while the formation of further disulfides gradually induces a structure more flexible with the structure of a molten globule for fully oxidized Gal-1. This finding is well-correlated with CPS results showing increasing peak H with increasing diamide concentration. A lower diamide:Gal-1 ratio leads to only a small increase of peak H while higher diamide concentration induces higher structural changes with more accessible electroactive residues for electrode reaction accompanied by values of peak H for denatured and unfolded form (Figs. 3 and 4). Contrary to diamide treatment, the peak H of Gal-1 reduced with TCEP slightly decreases with increased TCEP excess (Fig. 4C, D) accompanied by a decrease of bands' intensities representing dimers (Fig. 4G, H) in good agreement with previous observations [9,13,38].

3.3.2. Treatment time with diamide

Not only the concentration of diamide but also the incubation time results in structural changes of the Gal-1 (Fig. 5). As we mentioned above, Gal-1 forms monomers or dimers depending on experimental conditions, where the dimerization constant for wild-type Gal-1 was found between 1 and 7 μM [5,6,38]. Most of the mentioned studies focused on understanding the monomer/dimer ratio using wild type as a dimer and mutant representing monomer form [39]. The drawback of these studies is the fact, that monomeric mutants of Gal-1 can have changed the structure as well as binding affinity. However, results with mutated forms correlate with experiments studying immunomodulatory signaling showing a lack of Gal-1 activity when its monomer/dimer ratio is shifted to monomeric form and it happened for Gal-1 concentrations less than 1 μM [39].

To analyze the relation between oxidized Gal-1 and its monomeric or dimeric state, we tested the behavior of Gal-1 at different concentrations. Peaks H for Gal-1 incubated with equimolar concentration of diamide in Gal-1 concentration 2 μM and 14 μM , respectively, were compared. The monomeric form is more abundant at 2 μM Gal-1 concentration, whereas the abundance of dimeric form is higher at 14 μM Gal-1 concentration [40]. Since CPS peak H is dependent on protein concentration, the concentration of Gal-1 varied only during the incubation, the CPS measurements were performed at the same Gal-1 concentration, of 2 μM . Changes in CPS peak H height incubated with diamide in 2 μM concentrations are much more pronounced than for Gal-1 incubated with diamide at a concentration of 14 μM (Fig. 5A, B) suggesting a more structurally stable dimeric form. It is interesting that besides the zone for native Gal-1 (Fig. 5) is quite well recognizing zone, which could represent the formation of disulfide C16–C88. This oxidation was described as the first forming disulfide [17] and the formation of this disulfide is essential for the next disulfide formations [13]. Boundary for other oxidation forms of dimers are not such nicely recognized, probably due to the formation of a mixture of variously oxidized Gal-1 in monomeric/dimeric forms.

After 660 min incubation of Gal-1 with diamide, we also analyzed peak S to obtain information about the oxidation of Cys residues. Peaks S of untreated/native Gal-1 incubated at 2 μM and 14 μM showed similar heights, both at potential -0.58 V. However, 11-hour incubation with diamide led to the shift of both peaks S to -0.66 V due to forming disulfide bonds [27]. Additionally, incubation at 14 μM diamide concentration induced peak S decrease. These data suggest that the Cys oxidation occurs in both samples, but they behave differently adsorbed at the surface. Lower peak S of oxidized Gal-1 incubated at 14 μM concentration points to hindered accessibility of Cys-Cys residues, which can be due to a change of Gal-1 conformation in dimeric form and its different orientation at the surface. At the same time, these samples incubated at higher concentrations (Fig. 5B) seem to be more resistant to the effect of an electric field since they yield smaller peaks H which can

be explained by the higher stability of the dimeric structure. This finding, contradicts the established theory, assuming that oxidation of Gal-1 dimers leads to their disintegration into monomers or association into aggregates [10]. However, no significant increase of higher aggregate presence and decrease of dimers were observed at PAGE and Western blot data (Figs. 3 and 4E–H).

3.4. Lectin activity - the interaction of Gal-1 with its natural ligands

N-acetylglucosamine (LacNAc) belongs to the natural ligands of Gal-1. We tested its ability to interact with TCEP/diamide-treated Gal-1, utilizing protein intrinsic fluorescence [31]. Since carbohydrate-Gal-1 interactions are relatively weak, quite a high excess of saccharides should be present during the experiment [41]. Besides binding with Gal-1, saccharides are osmolytes [42], which nonspecifically influence the organization of the water environment of proteins. The addition of an excess of non-binding saccharides minimizes the nonspecific effects induced by the presence of specific binding saccharides [43]. The fluorescence experiments were performed in 1000-fold excess of glucose to Gal-1. The excess of glucose does not influence the distribution of monomers and dimers according to mobility shift assays (Fig. 6A). 9 μM Gal-1 was titrated with LacNAc in the presence of 9 mM glucose and after 5 min incubation, fluorescence spectra were recorded (Fig. 6B). Fluorescence intensity was normalized (see more details in Experimental) to minimize the effect of structural changes in oxidized and reduced form. The dissociation constant, K_D value for Gal-1, calculated using the one site-specific binding model [31] was 79 ± 11 μM . Similarly, Gal-1 was incubated overnight with 108 μM TCEP or diamide. Fluorescence spectra for reduced Gal-1 were about 12 % higher than those for oxidized Gal-1 (Fig. 6B Inset).

The K_D value for TCEP-treated Gal-1 of 64 ± 7 μM , was lower than for oxidized form, $K_D = 123 \pm 29$ μM . A similar trend was described for another specifically binding sugar, lactose, which binds with higher affinity to the reduced form of Gal-1 [9]. We were interested to see if we would obtain similar K_D values when we performed experiments at different Gal-1 concentrations, where we expect a different distribution of monomeric and dimeric forms at the same Gal-1 – diamide ratio of 1 to 12. The K_D for oxidized Gal-1 is almost 2 times higher than for the reduced form at 2 μM Gal-1 concentration (Fig. 6C). Increasing Gal-1 concentrations between 2 and 14 μM resulted in greater differences in K_D for reduced and oxidized Gal-1 (Fig. 6C, Scheme 1), which could be due to moving the monomer-dimer equilibrium towards dimer formation [40], as mentioned above. We performed also control experiments with 2 μM Gal-1 and the concentration of diamide, of 168 μM (ratio 1 to 84), same as for experiments with 14 μM Gal-1 to find if the changing of K_D is not the effect of high concentration of diamide. However, we observed a similar value of K_D as to ratio 1 to 12 (not shown).

K_D value at higher concentrations of reduced Gal-1 decreases (gray in

Fig. 5. Time-dependence of diamide oxidation of Gal-1. A., B. Distribution of CPS peak H height at different incubation times. A. 2 μM Gal-1 incubated with 2 μM diamide. Individual line might represent native – n, denatured – D, and unfolded Gal-1 – U. B. 14 μM Gal-1 incubated with 14 μM diamide. 14 μM Gal-1 was diluted to a concentration of 2 μM , 5 min before the measurement. C. Peaks S of Gal-1 (black) and Gal-1 incubated 660 min with diamide (red) at equimolar concentrations 2 μM (full line) and 14 μM (dashed line).

Fig. 6. Lectin activity of Gal-1. A. CBB G250 staining non-reducing 12.5 % acrylamide gel and Western blot of Gal-1 (gray), Gal-1 treated with TCEP (blue) and diamide (red) in the absence and presence of glucose. B. Dependence of normalized fluorescence intensity of 9 μM Gal-1 on *N*-acetyllactosamine concentration measured in PBS buffer in the presence of 9 mM glucose. Inset: Fluorescence spectra of Gal-1 treated with TCEP/diamide without the *N*-acetyllactosamine addition. C. K_D values for different concentrations of Gal-1 treated with TCEP/diamide overnight, titrated with LacNAc. All fluorescence spectroscopy experiments were performed with the same Gal-1-TCEP/diamide ratio of 1 to 12.

Scheme 1. Effect of lectin activity in dependence of Gal-1 concentration in its reduced (gray) and oxidized (pink) form.

(Scheme 1), which corresponds well with the fact that the dimeric form binds LacNAc more strongly than the monomeric form [9,10,13]. One reason for this is that the dissociation rate for dimers is slower than for monomers at the same association rates [6]. In contrast, the increasing concentration of oxidized Gal-1 results in a significant increase in K_D and a decrease in affinity to *N*-acetyllactosamine (Fig. 6B, pink in Scheme 1). According to [10], the Gal-1 oxidation leads to disaggregation to monomeric form or aggregate forming. If Gal-1 dimers would dissociate into monomers, K_D values for all concentrations of Gal-1 should be similar but the K_D is changing with the Gal-1 concentration. Ten times higher K_D for the samples with a higher abundance of dimers than monomers could be explained by Gal-1 aggregation. However, non-reducing PAGE with 45 μM (more than 3 \times times higher concentration than for fluorescence, Fig. 2) and with 20 μM (similar concentration,

Fig. 4) does not confirm the massive appearance of higher aggregates in oxidized samples compared to reduced ones. Also, Ippel et al. [16] showed using the diffusing coefficient measurements, in their very recent work, that Gal-1 dimers do not completely dissociate after their full oxidation. So, we suppose that Gal-1 oxidation might not lead to the dissociation of dimers to monomers, but probably induced structural changes diminishing lectin activity.

The non-reducing PAGE shows three bands for oxidized Gal-1 monomer and changes in bands representing dimers in comparison to reduced Gal-1 (Figs. 3 and 4). However, it is unclear how many variants of oxidized Gal-1 are in the dimeric forms and how individual oxidized forms bind the ligands. Our study is not able to fully explain the relationship between monomeric/dimeric and reduced/oxidized forms of Gal-1 but provides additional insights into this complicated issue. Further experiments should be done at concentration allowing the experiments closer to monomer/dimer equilibrium, i.e. at units of μM concentrations since our utilized methods and approaches are in the border of detection limits.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we attempt to merge two frequently described processes associated with the Gal-1 function. The first is monomer/dimer equilibrium and the second process is connected with oxidative changes of Gal-1. Biological functions of Gal-1 are predominantly linked with its reduced state [8] although it was also described that oxidized Gal-1 plays an important role during peripheral nerve regeneration, both, in vitro and in vivo [44]. Up to now, most in vitro experiments were performed (i) with methods, where significantly higher concentrations are necessary for experiments far from monomer/dimer equilibrium [5,38] and/or (ii) with Gal-1 mutant forms [9,13] where Cys residues were replaced by serines ones. Kane et al. [39] observed, that the serine mutation can alter the structure of wild-type Gal-1 and therefore the results may be distorted. In this work, we used chronopotentiometric stripping analysis, and intrinsic fluorescence spectroscopy, which allowed the study of Gal-1 at concentrations closer to monomer-dimer equilibrium [26,31]. CPS analysis is able to point out on small structural changes in protein as was mentioned in the Introduction. However, other methods are necessary for the elucidation of the processes (oxidation/reduction, dimerization) since the description of processes at

the surfaces is even more complicated at the surfaces than in solutions. CPS analysis showed that the time dependence of Gal-1 oxidation differs for samples with a higher abundance of monomers (Fig. 5A, B). Intrinsic fluorescence also provided information about the changing lectin activity depending on the reduced and oxidized Gal-1 concentration. LacNAc affinity increased for reduced Gal-1 form with increasing concentrations and is in good agreement with many previous findings [9,10]. Significantly higher K_D values were observed for oxidized Gal-1, additionally, the K_D values increased with increasing concentrations of oxidized Gal-1 opposite to reduced Gal-1. The processes of reduced Gal-1 are well-described in literature, where the individual results complement each other, including ours. However, processes linked with oxidized Gal-1 are less clear. According to the literature, oxidized Gal-1 disaggregates to monomers or forms aggregates [10,45]. Our experiments complemented by mobility shift assays showed neither a significant increase in Gal-1 aggregates nor disaggregation of dimers. Different results in published works [9,12,13] could be caused by different experimental conditions, for example, concentration. Most in vitro methods are sensitive in the tens of micromolar concentration ranges, often far from in vivo conditions. Further, the experiments were done with mutants that may behave differently from wild-type Gal-1 [39]. We suppose that mild oxidation of Gal-1 does not result in the huge dissociation of dimers to monomers, but only leads to structural changes of dimeric form. Structural changes induced by oxidation are unfavorable for carbohydrate binding. In addition, our experiments show that several tested commercial monoclonal antibodies from different sources bind more strongly to dimers than to monomers. Comparison of non-reducing PAGE with Western blot (Figs. 3 and 4) clearly shows that the used antibody binds only one type of oxidized monomers. Our findings are necessary to consider in experiments in vivo, where Gal-1 can be affected by oxidative conditions. This could have important implications for a number of cellular processes, for example in the tumor microenvironment, where Gal-1, as a multivalent carbohydrate-binding protein, may mediate glycoprotein binding to the extracellular matrix under specific conditions and inhibit adhesion and promote metastasis under other redox conditions.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tatiana Staroňová: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Jitka Holčáková:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Petr Voňka:** Visualization, Data curation. **Roman Hrstka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis. **Veronika Ostatná:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Not applicable.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Funding

This research was supported by the Czech Science Foundation by project No. 22-26590S, by MH CZ - DRO (MMCI, 00209805) and by the project National Institute for Cancer Research (Programme EXCELES, ID Project No. LX22NPO5102) - Funded by the European Union - Next Generation EU.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Veronika Ostatna reports financial support was provided by Czech Science Foundation. Roman Hrstka reports financial support was provided by Ministry of Health of the Czech Republic. Roman Hrstka reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

- [1] S. Di Lella, V. Sundblad, J.P. Cerliani, C.M. Guardia, D.A. Estrin, G.R. Vasta, G. A. Rabinovich, When galectins recognize glycans: from biochemistry to physiology and back again, *Biochemistry* 50 (37) (2011) 7842–7857.
- [2] H. Leffler, S. Carlsson, M. Hedlund, Y.N. Qian, F. Poirier, Introduction to galectins, *Glycoconj. J.* 19 (7–9) (2002) 433–440.
- [3] J.C. Sacchettini, L.G. Baum, C.F. Brewer, Multivalent protein-carbohydrate interactions. A new paradigm for supermolecular assembly and signal transduction, *Biochemistry* 40 (10) (2001) 3009–3015.
- [4] R.D. Cummings, F.-T. Liu, G.A. Rabinovich, S.R. Stowell, G.R. Vasta, Galectins, in: A. Varki, R.D. Cummings, J.D. Esko, P. Stanley, G.W. Hart, M. Aebi, D. Mohnen, T. Kinoshita, N.H. Packer, J.H. Prestegard, R.L. Schnaar, P.H. Seeberger (Eds.), *Essentials of Glycobiology*, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor (NY), 2022. Copyright © 2022 by the Consortium of Glycobiology Editors, La Jolla, California. Published by Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor, New York. All rights reserved.
- [5] E. Salomonsson, A. Larumbe, J. Tejler, E. Tullberg, H. Rydberg, A. Sundin, A. Khabut, T. Frejd, Y.D. Lobsanov, J.M. Rini, U.J. Nilsson, H. Leffler, Monovalent interactions of galectin-1, *Biochemistry* 49 (44) (2010) 9518–9532.
- [6] J.M. Romero, M. Trujillo, D.A. Estrin, G.A. Rabinovich, S. Di Lella, Impact of human galectin-1 binding to saccharide ligands on dimer dissociation kinetics and structure, *Glycobiology* 26 (12) (2016) 1317–1327.
- [7] Y. Nonaka, T. Ogawa, H. Shoji, N. Nishi, S. Kamitori, T. Nakamura, Crystal structure and conformational stability of a galectin-1 tandem-repeat mutant with a short linker, *Glycobiology* 32 (3) (2022) 251–259.
- [8] I. Camby, M. Le Mercier, F. Lefranc, R. Kiss, Galectin-1: a small protein with major functions, *Glycobiology* 16 (11) (2006) 137R–157R.
- [9] S.R. Stowell, M.J. Cho, C.L. Feasley, C.M. Arthur, X.Z. Song, J.K. Colucci, S. Karmakar, P. Mehta, M. Dias-Baruffi, R.P. McEver, R.D. Cummings, Ligand reduces galectin-1 sensitivity to oxidative inactivation by enhancing dimer formation, *J. Biol. Chem.* 284 (8) (2009) 4989–4999.
- [10] C.M. Arthur, M.D. Baruffi, R.D. Cummings, S.R. Stowell, Evolving mechanistic insights into galectin functions, in: S.R. Stowell, R.D. Cummings (Eds.), *Galectins: Methods and Protocols*, 2015, pp. 1–35.
- [11] C.P. Modenutti, J.I.B. Capurro, S. Di Lella, M.A. Martf, The structural biology of galectin-ligand recognition: current advances in modeling tools, protein engineering, and inhibitor design, *Front. Chem.* 7 (2019).
- [12] M.F. López-Lucendo, D. Solís, S. André, J. Hirabayashi, K.-I. Kasai, H. Kaltner, H.-J. Gabius, A. Romero, Growth-regulatory human galectin-1: crystallographic characterisation of the structural changes induced by single-site mutations and their impact on the thermodynamics of ligand binding, *J. Mol. Biol.* 343 (4) (2004) 957–970.
- [13] C.M. Guardia, J.J. Caramelo, M. Trujillo, S.P. Mendez-Huergo, R. Radi, D.A. Estrin, G.A. Rabinovich, Structural basis of redox-dependent modulation of galectin-1 dynamics and function, *Glycobiology* 24 (5) (2014) 428–441.
- [14] N. Ahmad, H.J. Gabius, H. Kaltner, S. André, I. Kuwabara, F.T. Liu, S. Oscarson, T. Norberg, C.F. Brewer, Thermodynamic binding studies of cell surface carbohydrate epitopes to galectins-1, -3, and -7: evidence for differential binding specificities, *Can. J. Chem.* 80 (8) (2002) 1096–1104.
- [15] G.R. Vasta, H. Ahmed, *Animal Lectins*, CRC Press, 2008.
- [16] G. Ferrer-Sueta, B. Manta, H. Botti, R. Radi, M. Trujillo, A. Denicola, Factors affecting protein thiol reactivity and specificity in peroxide reduction, *Chem. Res. Toxicol.* 24 (4) (2011) 434–450.
- [17] H. Ippel, M.C. Miller, R.P.M. Dings, A.-K. Ludwig, H.-J. Gabius, K.H. Mayo, Cysteine oxidation in human galectin-1 occurs sequentially via a folded intermediate to a fully oxidized unfolded form, *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 25 (13) (2024) 6956.
- [18] L.B. Clerch, P. Whitney, M. Hass, K. Brew, T. Miller, R. Werner, D. Massaro, Sequence of a full-length cDNA for rat lung beta-galactoside-binding protein - primary and secondary structure of the lectin, *Biochemistry* 27 (2) (1988) 692–699.

- [19] A.H. Pande, R.K. Gupta, Sumati, K. Hajela, Oxidation of goat hepatic galectin-1 induces change in secondary structure, *Protein Peptide Lett.* 10 (3) (2003) 265–275.
- [20] J. Hirabayashi, K. Kasai, Effect of amino-acid substitution by site-directed mutagenesis on the carbohydrate recognition and stability of human 14-kDa beta-galactoside-binding lectin, *J. Biol. Chem.* 266 (35) (1991) 23648–23653.
- [21] E. Paleček, J. Tkáč, M. Bartosík, T. Bertok, V. Ostatná, J. Paleček, Electrochemistry of nonconjugated proteins and glycoproteins. Toward sensors for biomedicine and glycomics, *Chem. Rev.* 115 (5) (2015) 2045–2108.
- [22] V. Ostatná, H. Cernocká, T. Galicová, S. Hason, Electrochemical analysis of proteins important in cancer: behavior of anterior gradient receptors, p53 protein and their complexes at charged surfaces, *Curr. Opin. Electrochem.* 39 (2023) 101269.
- [23] J. Vacek, M. Zatloukalová, V. Dorcák, M. Cifra, Z. Futera, V. Ostatná, Electrochemistry in sensing of molecular interactions of proteins and their behavior in an electric field, *Microchim. Acta* 190 (11) (2023) 442.
- [24] L. Rimankova, H. Cernocká, E. Tihlarikova, V. Nedela, V. Ostatná, Chronopotentiometric sensing of native, oligomeric, denatured and aggregated serum albumin at charged surfaces, *Bioelectrochemistry* 145 (2022).
- [25] H. Cernocká, V. Ostatná, E. Paleček, Fast-scan cyclic voltammetry with thiol-modified mercury electrodes distinguishes native from denatured BSA, *Electrochem. Commun.* 61 (2015) 114–116.
- [26] E. Paleček, V. Ostatná, Electroactivity of nonconjugated proteins and peptides. Towards electroanalysis of all proteins, *Electroanalysis* 19 (2007) 2383–2403.
- [27] R. Kizek, J. Vacek, L. Trnková, F. Jelen, Cyclic voltammetric study of the redox system of glutathione using the disulfide bond reductant tris(2-carboxyethyl) phosphine, *Bioelectrochemistry* 63 (1–2) (2004) 19–24.
- [28] M.J. Honeychurch, M.J. Ridd, The effect of a nonadsorbing electroactive species on the transition time in derivative adsorptive chronopotentiometric stripping analysis, *Electroanalysis* 7 (11) (1995) 1041–1047.
- [29] M. Heyrovský, P. Mader, S. Vavrická, V. Vesela, M. Fedurco, The anodic reactions at mercury electrodes due to cysteine, *J. Electroanal. Chem.* 430 (1–2) (1997) 103–117.
- [30] J.E. Tropea, S. Cherry, D.S. Waugh, Expression and purification of soluble His(6)-tagged TEV protease, *Methods Mol. Biol.* 498 (2009) 297–307.
- [31] P. Sindrewicz, X.X. Li, E.A. Yates, J.E. Turnbull, L.Y. Lian, L.G. Yu, Intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence spectroscopy reliably determines galectin-ligand interactions, *Sci. Rep.* 9 (2019).
- [32] E. Paleček, V. Ostatná, Ionic strength-dependent structural transition of proteins at electrode surfaces, *ChemComm* 13 (2009) 1685–1687.
- [33] J.A. Burns, J.C. Butler, J. Moran, G.M. Whitesides, Selective reduction of disulfides by tris(2-carboxyethyl)phosphine, *J. Org. Chem.* 56 (8) (1991) 2648–2650.
- [34] N.S. Kosower, E.M. Kosower, Thiol labeling with bromobimanes, *Methods Enzymol.* 143 (1987) 76–84.
- [35] V. Vargová, R.E. Giménez, H. Cernocká, D.C. Trujillo, F. Tulli, V.I.P. Zanini, E. Paleček, C.D. Borsarelli, V. Ostatná, Label-free electrochemical detection of singlet oxygen protein damage, *Electrochim. Acta* 187 (2016) 662–669.
- [36] J.R. Stone, S.P. Yang, Hydrogen peroxide: a signaling messenger, *Antioxid. Redox Signal.* 8 (3–4) (2006) 243–270.
- [37] C.D. Borsarelli, L.J. Falomir-Lockhart, V. Ostatná, J.A. Fauerbach, H.H. Hsiao, H. Urlaub, E. Paleček, E.A. Jares-Erijman, T.M. Jovin, Biophysical properties and cellular toxicity of covalent crosslinked oligomers of alpha-synuclein formed by photoinduced side-chain tyrosyl radicals, *Free Radic. Biol. Med.* 53 (4) (2012) 1004–1015.
- [38] A. Leppänen, S. Stowell, O. Blixt, R.D. Cummings, Dimeric galectin-1 binds with high affinity to α 2,3-sialylated and non-sialylated terminal *N*-acetylglucosamine units on surface-bound extended glycans, *J. Biol. Chem.* 280 (7) (2005) 5549–5562.
- [39] B.J. Kane, M.M. Fettes, S.A. Farhadi, R.J. Liu, G.A. Hudalla, Site-specific cross-linking of galectin-1 homodimers via poly(ethylene glycol) bismaleimide, *Cell. Mol. Bioeng.* 14 (5) (2021) 523–534.
- [40] M. Cho, R.D. Cummings, Characterization of monomeric forms of galectin-1 generated by site-directed mutagenesis, *Biochemistry* 35 (40) (1996) 13081–13088.
- [41] J.F.K. James Andrew Goodrich, *Binding and Kinetics for Molecular Biologists*, First edition ed, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, 2007.
- [42] L.R. Singh, N.K. Poddar, T.A. Dar, R. Kumar, F. Ahmad, Protein and DNA destabilization by osmolytes: the other side of the coin, *Life Sci.* 88 (3–4) (2011) 117–125.
- [43] T. Galicová, S. Hason, V. Ostatná, Interaction of lectin *Sambucus nigra* with sialylated trisaccharides in the presence of osmolytes. Chronopotentiometric sensing, *Bioelectrochemistry* 152 (2023).
- [44] H. Horie, T. Kadoya, K. Sang, M. Hasegawa, Oxidized galectin-1 is an essential factor for peripheral nerve regeneration, *Curr. Drug Targets* 6 (4) (2005) 385–394.
- [45] B.S. Robinson, C.M. Arthur, B. Evavold, E. Roback, N.A. Kamili, C.S. Stowell, M. L. Vallecillo-Zuniga, P.M. Van Ry, M. Dias-Baruffi, R.D. Cummings, S.R. Stowell, The sweet-side of leukocytes: galectins as master regulators of neutrophil function, *Front. Immunol.* 10 (2019).